

IMPLEMENTING ECG-BASED DETECTION FOR SLEEP APNEA

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ABSTRACT : Many people have a sleep disorder called sleep apnea, which can cause health problems. It's important to find this condition early, and doctors usually do a test called a polysomnography (PSG). But what if that test isn't available? This study looked at building a system to check for sleep apnea using two simpler tests: an electrocardiogram (ECG) and a blood oxygen test (SpO₂). The system uses a special program to tell the difference between normal sleep and sleep apnea. By testing this system on a group of people, the researchers found it could be 95% accurate. This suggests that using ECG and SpO₂ together could be a good way to find sleep apnea, offering an alternative to traditional methods.

Keywords: OSA (Obstructive Sleep Apnea), ECG (Electrocardiogram), SpO₂ (Blood Oxygen Saturation), PSG (Polysomnography), RF (Random Forest).

I. INTRODUCTION

Sleep Apnea is a major public health issue characterized by pauses in breathing or low breathing volumes during sleep. The brief pauses in breathing, i.e., apneas, occur when the throat muscles intermittently relax and block the airway, thus momentarily disturbing the sleep pattern, during some time in the sleep. It has its complications on cardiovascular diseases, cognitive impairments, and even lowering the quality of life among many others, not just in disturbed sleep. This, therefore, would call for early detection and effective management of sleep apnea, which has a high rate of prevalence and predisposes people to health risks.

Polysomnography (PSG) is an overnight, labour-intensive procedure monitoring a wide array of physiologic parameters during sleep. It is generally considered the gold standard by which all other diagnostic techniques are compared.

However, with so much of its detailed effectiveness, PSG has its cons that make it expensive, needing special conditions for its conducting and being quite invasive from the patient's point of view. Limitations can reinforce the concept of the exigent necessity for alternative diagnostic approaches, which can provide them with the much-needed efficiency without compromising their accessibility and invasion. More recently, modern progress in biomedical engineering with the convergence of machine learning has led to innovative diagnostic techniques. Researchers are excited about using simpler tests like electrocardiograms (ECG) and blood oxygen tests (SpO₂) to track sleep apnea. These tests are easier on patients and less expensive than the traditional sleep test (PSG). By studying these signals in more detail, doctors might be able to find sleep apnea in a way that's less uncomfortable and cheaper, making it easier for people to get diagnosed.

This research tackles the challenge of finding sleep apnea easily and without needles or uncomfortable tests (traditional PSG method). They propose a new way to find sleep apnea using advanced computer programs (machine learning) that work with the information from simple tests like electrocardiograms (ECG) and blood oxygen tests (SpO₂). This system can tell the difference between normal breathing and sleep apnea events. Their method is very accurate and can be used by many people, unlike the traditional sleep test. Overall, the researchers want to find sleep apnea quickly and easily to improve people's health.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

- [1] **Optimization of sleep apnea detection using SpO₂ and ANN:** This study delves into the significant impact of sleep disruptions, which can lead to inadequate nighttime sleep and daytime fatigue, profoundly affecting individuals' lives. Addressing two crucial challenges in sleep analysis, it focuses on accurately scoring sleep stages and detecting apnea-hypopnea events. Hypopnea, characterized by a reduction in oronasal airflow and blood oxygen desaturation, is defined with specific parameters. The classification of apneas into obstructive sleep apnea (OSA), mixed sleep apnea (MSA), and central sleep apnea (CSA)

follows expert recommendations. Early detection of hypopnea-apnea events during deep sleep is emphasized to prevent cardiopulmonary failure. The proposed system employs EEG signal measurements to determine approximate entropy, demonstrating high sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy, thus providing an automated solution for timely detection. Limitations include a small sample size and the absence of comparative analysis with existing detection methods for sleep apnea-hypopnea syndrome.

[2] **An Efficient Method to Detect Sleep Hypopnea- Apnea Events Based on EEG Signals:**

Sleep apnea (SA) is a prevalent sleep disorder characterized by respiratory disturbances during sleep, typically diagnosed using polysomnography (PSG), which is time-consuming and costly. This study explores a real-time SA detection system utilizing oxygen saturation (SpO₂) and electrocardiogram (ECG) signals individually and in combination. R-R intervals from raw ECG data are input into a feed-forward deep artificial neural network for SA detection. Three models using SpO₂ and R-R interval signals showed superior performance, with the SpO₂-based model achieving higher sensitivity. Utilizing Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) and Continuous Wavelet Transform (CWT) for Time-Frequency Representation (TFR), the study focuses on analysing nonstationary signals. For apnea detection, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) integrate scalogram and spectrogram images of one-minute ECG segments, emphasizing the importance of combining multiple TFRs for enhanced discriminative information. Employing a residual learning approach with skip connections in the CNN architecture, the study proposes an obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) classification, addressing gradient vanishing and enabling learning of complex representations. Limitations include the ECG-based model's lower accuracy due to an erroneous QRS detector and reliance on specific algorithms for QRS detection and feature extraction, potentially limiting generalizability. Additionally, the study's reliance on a limited sample size raises concerns about result generalizability to a larger population.

[3] **Detection of Sleep Apnea from Electrocardiogram and Pulse Oximetry Signals Using**

Random Forest: Sleep apnea (SA) is a prevalent sleep disorder known to impact individuals' physiological well-being, emphasizing the importance of early detection for health mitigation. Conventional diagnostic methods like polysomnography (PSG) may not always be readily available, necessitating exploration into automatic SA detection with a reduced signal set. By integrating these signals using recursive feature elimination with

cross-validation (RFECV) and employing a random forest (RF) classifier, the algorithm achieved high sensitivity and specificity on the Apnea-ECG database, outperforming previous methodologies. Results underscored the complementary nature of ECG and SpO₂ in SA detection, highlighting the potential of their combination. While the proposed system offers a promising alternative to traditional diagnostic methods, future endeavours will focus on addressing limitations such as discrimination of apnea from hypoventilation events and expanding dataset integration for improved validation. The study aims to fill a notable gap in sleep apnea detection research by leveraging innovative signal fusion techniques for enhanced diagnostic accuracy.

III. ALGORITHMS

This section dives into a specific method called the Decision Tree Algorithm. Imagine a series of questions you might ask to identify something, like a type of animal. The Decision Tree Algorithm works like this question-and-answer process, but for sorting things into groups (classification) or predicting values (regression). It builds a structure with branching paths, like a tree. Each branch represents a decision based on a specific feature of the thing you're trying to identify. By following these branches and answering the questions, you eventually reach an answer at the end, which is the group or value the data belongs to. The algorithm keeps asking the most important question at each step to efficiently sort the data into increasingly similar groups based on what you're trying to find.

Algorithm 1: Decision Tree

```
1. from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier
2. DecisionTree = DecisionTreeClassifier(criterion="entropy",random_state=2,max_depth=5)
3. DecisionTree.fit(Xtrain,Ytrain)
4. predicted_values = DecisionTree.predict(Xtest)
5. x = metrics.accuracy_score(Ytest, predicted_values)
6. acc.append(x)
7. model.append('Decision Tree')
8. print("DecisionTrees's Accuracy is: ", x*100)
9. print(classification_report(Ytest,predicted_values))
```

2. Naïve Bayes algorithm: The Naïve Bayes algorithm is a probabilistic classification technique based on Bayes' theorem and conditional probability. It assumes that the features are conditionally independent given the class label, simplifying the computation of class probabilities. Despite its simplicity and strong independence assumption, Naïve Bayes often performs well in practice, especially in text classification and other high-dimensional datasets.

Algorithm 2: Gaussian Naïve Bayes

```
1. from sklearn.naive_bayes import GaussianNB
2. NaiveBayes = GaussianNB()
3. NaiveBayes.fit(Xtrain,Ytrain)
4. predicted_values = NaiveBayes.predict(Xtest)
5. x = metrics.accuracy_score(Ytest, predicted_values)
6. acc.append(x)
7. model.append('Naive Bayes')
8. print("Naive Bayes's Accuracy is: ", x)
9. print(classification_report(Ytest,predicted_values))
```

3.Support Vector Machine Algorithm: In tasks concerning regression and classification, the Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithm serves as a supervised learning method. Its objective is to pinpoint the optimal hyperplane within a multidimensional space to segregate data points across different classifications. Through the utilization of diverse kernel functions to project input data into higher-dimensional feature spaces, SVM adeptly deals with both linear and non-linear datasets. Its primary approach involves maximizing the margin between classes, which essentially defines the decision boundary.

Algorithm 3: Support Vector Machine (SVM)

```
1. from sklearn.svm import SVC
2. from sklearn.preprocessing import MinMaxScaler
3. norm = MinMaxScaler().fit(Xtrain)
4. norm = MinMaxScaler().fit(Xtrain)
5. X_train_norm = norm.transform(Xtrain)
6. X_test_norm = norm.transform(Xtest)
7. SVM = SVC(kernel='poly', degree=3, C=1)
8. SVM.fit(X_train_norm,Ytrain)
9. predicted_values = SVM.predict(X_test_norm)
10. x = metrics.accuracy_score(Ytest, predicted_values)
11. acc.append(x)
12. model.append('SVM')
13. print("SVM's Accuracy is: ", x)
14. print(classification_report(Ytest,predicted_values))
```

4. Random Forest algorithm: Imagine a forest full of decision trees, like the one described earlier. A Random Forest algorithm is like having a group of experts, each using their own decision tree to identify something. To make a final call, the algorithm listens to all the experts (trees) and picks the most popular answer (for classification problems) or takes the average of their predictions (for regression problems). Each expert is trained on a slightly different set of data and questions, making them more diverse. By combining their knowledge, the forest gets a more accurate and reliable answer, while avoiding getting stuck on one specific idea (overfitting).

Algorithm 4: Random Forest

```
1. from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
2. RF = RandomForestClassifier(n_estimators=20, random_state=0)
3. RF.fit(Xtrain,Ytrain)
4. predicted_values = RF.predict(Xtest)
5. x = metrics.accuracy_score(Ytest, predicted_values)
6. acc.append(x)
7. model.append('RF')
8. print("RF's Accuracy is: ", x)
9. print(classification_report(Ytest,predicted_values))
```

IV. DATASETS

The Sleep Health and Lifestyle Dataset is comprised of 400 entries and 13 attributes, encompassing a diverse array of factors associated with sleep patterns and everyday behaviours. It encompasses information such as gender, age, profession, duration and quality of sleep, level of physical activity, stress levels, BMI classification, blood pressure, heart rate, daily step count, and whether someone has a medically recognized sleep disorder..

V. METHEDODOLOGY

Figure 1. Data Flow & Processing

1. **SENSORS:** In sleep apnea detection using ECG, we use sensors like stickers placed on the body to catch electrical signals from the heart. These signals can tell us about breathing problems that might be happening during sleep. The information from these sensors is then analyzed by computers to find patterns that show sleep apnea and separate them from normal sleep patterns.

2. **ESP32 board:** A small computer called an ESP32 board, which is often used in electronic devices, can be helpful for sleep apnea detection using ECG signals. By connecting with ECG sensors and using special programs, the ESP32 can analyze ECG data as it happens, allowing for the detection of apnea events without needing traditional sleep studies.

3. **ThingSpeak:** ThingSpeak is an online service that can be used to collect, analyze, and visualize data from the body, including ECG signals, for sleep apnea detection. Researchers can put information streams from wearable devices or medical sensors into ThingSpeak,

allowing for real-time monitoring and analysis of sleep patterns and apnea events without needing traditional sleep studies.

VI. RESULTS

ACCURACY COMPARISON:

Figure 2. Comparison of accuracy

PREDICTED OUTPUT:

Three classifications based on the input values:

Figure 3. Classification – Normal

Figure 4. Classification – Insomnia

Figure 5. Classification – Sleep Apnea

VII. CONCLUSION

Sleep apnea is a serious sleep disorder that affects many people around the world. The current way doctors diagnose it requires a night spent in a sleep lab, which can be expensive and uncomfortable. This research looked into a new way to detect sleep apnea using signals from the body that are easy to measure during sleep, like heart rhythm and oxygen levels. These signals are analyzed by special computer programs that can learn to identify patterns linked to sleep apnea.

This novel approach holds promise for being significantly more convenient and cost-effective compared to conventional diagnostic methods. It has the potential to enable individuals to undergo sleep apnea testing either at home or in a clinical setting. This advancement could result in the early identification of the condition, a critical factor as untreated sleep apnea can lead to severe health complications. Early detection would facilitate timely intervention and treatment, enhancing the overall health and quality of life for individuals with sleep apnea.

The overarching aim of this research is to develop a portable and dependable tool for diagnosing sleep apnea. Such a tool could enable early detection of sleep apnea, facilitating improved monitoring and personalized treatment for those at risk.

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